

Grammatical Cohesion Conjunction Markers as Binders of Discourse Text Structure

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Abstract:- The cohesion and coherency of a discourse text structure is determined by the correct use of conjunction type grammatical cohesive markers, because these cohesive markers own the function of joining two clauses and sentences. The use of these conjunction type grammatical cohesive markers can also be found on Mandarin essay text written by the students of Mandarin Language Education Study Program, State University of Surabaya class of 2021. There are three types of conjunctions used in the essay written by students, which are, conjunction categorized as additive as a marker equivalent relationship is actualized by using the preposition 和 *hé* (and) as well as the use of preposition 也 *yě* (also, too) to indicate a relationship of emphasis and/or equality towards its parts. Category of clause conjunction is a category which plays the role to bind a cause-and-effect relationship, indicated by the use of preposition 因为 *yīnwéi* (because) as an indicator of cause and there is an annihilation on the indicator of effect or result, preposition 所以 *suǒyǐ* (so, therefore) as an indicator of effect or result and occurs an omission of the *cause* indicator, the preposition 当然 *dāngrán* (of course, certainly/absolutely) as a result indicator that does not require a *cause* preposition, and the use of preposition 因为 *yīnwéi* (because)... 所以 *suǒyǐ* (so, therefore) a standard form of casual relationship indicator/marker. And adversative category conjunctions are marked by the existent of preposition 不仅 *bùjǐn* (not only)... 而且 *érqiě* (but also), the use of preposition 而不仅仅因为 *ér bùjǐn jǐn yīnwèi* (not only because), preposition 但是 *dànshì* (but), and also preposition 尽管...但是 *jǐnguǎn... dànshì* (although... but) which marks and indicates a characteristic of conflict and denial relationship.

Keywords:- Cohesion Markers, Grammatical Cohesion, Conjunctions, Structural Integration, Discourse Texts.

I. INTRODUCTION

Language owns a central role when it comes to communicating, because through language, thoughts, feelings, and information can be conveyed. Arista & Subandi (2020: 714) mentioned, to deliver thoughts and ideas, language is used as a way to deliver in a communication. Through its creativity, language is used by humans in various forms and meanings by using language instruments such as the element of cohesion which used to form a coherence and integration of language structure. By that, for humans, language is an endless attempt of creativity (Dhieni & Fridani 2007: 3). The use of language in communication can be through written language which is a form of productive language skills, identified to deliver ideas, thoughts and feelings through writings. Masrur & Subandi (2020: 730) mentioned, “On the other hand, writing skill has a very important role in language learning because the writing is included in productive skill wich can be used as a medium of communication in the form of written language” (also view Hermaditoyo & Firna 2019: 22). Because of that, in a field of language learning, writing skills also taught with the intention to form student competencies in regards to the use of written language as a media to communicate (Noermanzah, 2019: 307). Writing is the highest level of language skills because a writer must be able to provide every language element which supports the aspects of creativity and efficiency in language. Therefore, writing skill also considered the most complex and difficult type of language skills (Arista & Subandi, 2020: 714). In a Mandarin language learning, there’s also thinking writing skills which writing essay texts. Unga Waeu et al (2022: 186) mentioned, in a process of learning the Mandarin language, the skill of composing essay text is an active and productive skills. By such means, writing skill owns a very important role in a language learning because writings included in productive skill which can be used as a media to communicate in a form of writing language (Subandi et al, 2020: 749).

Composing an essay needs to pay attention to the aspect of text structure's integration which very determined by the involvement of cohesive element. Itaristanti (2016: 89) stated, by paying attention to the element of cohesion and coherence, a discourse text's coherence can be conserved so the idea that's about to be conveyed could be understood by the readers. By means, cohesion tools have the central role in the composing of discourse text as a highest language level in a grammatical hierarchy. Subandi et al. (2022: 55) mentioned, a discourse is the highest level in a language hierarchy, not only consisted of sentences as basic constituent elements, but elements of a sentence need to be arrayed according to its certain rules which connected with the narrative flow so it would become a coherent depiction of events and stories as to form a whole and unified discourse text. Cohesion aspect makes elements that determine consistency of text's structure so that it becomes a unified whole be it in a relationship of forms or meanings, thus readers can grasp certain meaning of the writer's intentions. (Arista et al. 2023: 2103). Supported by the opinions of (Dini et al., 2022: 153), Gutwinsky (in Pernando & Rahima, 2017: 2), and Sumarlum et al. (2003: 23) cohesion is a relationship of forms or structures which is a relationship between sentences as a main element to form a discourse text, be it in grammatical level or lexical level. On the other side, Halliday & Hasan (1976: 6) differentiate cohesion into two types, which from the form (grammatical) and from the meaning (lexical).

The use of cohesion markers can be found in many written discourse texts. According to Sumarlum et al. (2003: 16) that written discourse is a discourse which conveyed in written language in which there is indirect communication between reader and the writer. One example of a written discourse text is an essay text composed by students of the 2021 Mandarin Language Education Study Program, State University of Surabaya as an assignment for the Advanced Mandarin Writing course. As a written discourse text, the essay composed by the student must also fulfil the elements of wholeness and coherence of the essay structure, which is marked by the relationship between sentences as elements which form the essay. Because a coherent and complete essay text represents the use of appropriate cohesive instrument, it will help facilitate the reader's understanding process.

According to the explanation above, the object of discussion in this article is bounded by conjunction type grammatical cohesion markers in the discourse text composed by students of the 2021 Mandarin Language Education Study Program State University of Surabaya. Thereafter will be studied how forms and the role of conjunction type grammatical cohesion marker's instrument in forming a structure of cohesive discourse text in an essay text composed by the student of the 2021 Mandarin Language Education of State University of Surabaya.

II. COHESION

Subandi, et al (2022) mentioned, on grammatical hierarchy discourse is the highest grammatical unit, thus it could be considered as a complete language unit because it has concept, ideas, or a whole complete thought (see also Chaer, 2014: 267; Sumarlum et al., 2003: 7; Izar et al., 2019: 56). On the other side, Djadjasudarma (2017: 2) opined, a whole and complete discourse needs to be supported by the coherence aspect in terms of content while cohesive aspect in terms of coherence of structural elements (see also Mulyana, 2005: 25). Citations above could be interpreted that discourse is the complete and highest grammatical unit which consists of cohesive element as a binder to form a cohesive discourse text structure.

The existent of cohesive instrument in a discourse text structure becomes an inevitability, because as a determining element in establishing coherence and unification of structure and meaning of discourse texts (Karadeniz, 2017; Djadjasudarma, 2017: 39). Other than that, Halliday & Hasan (1976: 4) explained, "The concept of cohesion is a semantic one; it refers to relations of meaning that exist within the text, and that define it as a text." Aligned with the opinion of Pengxia et al (2021: 536) "在他看来，衔接反映了句子之间的形式关系。在衔接的帮助下，句子之间的联系更加清晰和恰当" *zài tā kàn lái, xiánjiē fǎnyìng le jù zǐ zhī jiān de xíngshì guānxì. zài xiánjiē de bāngzhù xià, jù zǐ zhī jiān de liánxì gèngjiā qīngxī hé qiàdàng*. Mentioned that cohesion represents a formal relationship between sentences which makes the relation itself clearer and more precise (see also Talaumbanua, 2023: 46; Ashari et al., 2019: 106; Mulyana, 2005: 25). According to the citations above it is proven that the hint of cohesive markers in a discourse text takes role to form linearity relations between the elements of language in which form texts. And by means, cohesive marker in a discourse text is one of the central elements that also takes part determining types of relation, coherence aspect, as well as the harmony which resulting in a complete meaning of a discourse text (see also Darmawati, 2021: 299; Mulyana, 2005: 26).

III. CONJUNCTION TYPE GRAMMATICAL COHESION

One of the cohesive markers is a grammatical cohesion, which is the type that binders the relationship between forming element sentences of discourse texts based on grammatical structure (see also Ardiyanti & Setyorini, 2019: 8). Aligned with the opinion of Halliday & Hasan (1976: 6), "Grammatical cohesion is a semantic relation between elements that refers to grammatical structure." Which means, grammatical cohesion is a semantic relation between elements that refers to grammatical structures (see also Barru, 2017: 263). Furthermore, Halliday & Hasan, 1976: 6) explained that there are four types of grammatical cohesion, which one of the lists is the conjunction type.

Sumarlam et al., (2003: 32) explained that conjunction is a conjunctive or a way to connect one element with the other. The element refers to word, phrase, sentence, clause, and also the bigger elements. With the use of conjunctions, therefore, the relations between sentences will be clearer. Halliday & Hasan (1976: 238) classify conjunctions into four kinds, the three of all are additive conjunction, adversative conjunction, and causal conjunction. Additive one is the type of conjunction which connects two equivalent clauses by adding additional statement or explanation without changing the previous sentence. While the adversative conjunction or also known as contrast conjunction, is one that connects two contrasting clauses. Thus, the causal conjunction is one that connects two cause-and-effect clauses.

IV. METHOD

This study is considered as qualitative research because the applied data is a written descriptive one in the form of words, phrase and/or sentences which has a grammatical cohesion. The data obtained by the essay text written by the 2021 Mandarin Language Education Study Program of State University of Surabaya. Overall, the amount of 66 data cohesive grammatical conjunction type. Therefore, it is classified and obtained three types of conjunction, precisely presented on table 1. Thus, it is analysed then results are presented descriptively to gain an authentic and precise depiction regarding conjunction type of grammatical cohesion.

V. RESULTS

Presented below a result of data analysis in the use of cohesive grammatical instrument in a written text composed by the student as it is displayed on table 1, therefore, each instrument of cohesive markers be described as following.

Table.1 Grammatical Cohesion Conjunction Type

Categories of Conjunction		Number	
Additive	和 <i>hé</i>	9	24
	而 <i>ér</i>	2	
	然后 <i>ránhòu</i>	3	
	当然 <i>dāngrán</i>	3	
	也 <i>yě</i>	7	
Causal	因为 <i>yīnwéi</i>	8	22
	如果 <i>rúguǒ</i>	6	
	所以 <i>suǒyǐ</i>	8	
Adversative	不仅 <i>bùjǐn</i>	5	20
	而且 <i>érqiě</i>	3	
	而不仅仅因为 <i>ér bùjǐn jǐn yīnwéi</i>	2	
	尽管 <i>jǐnguǎn</i>	3	
	但是 <i>dànshì</i>	7	
Total		66	

A. Additive Conjunction

The category of additive conjunction in the text composed by the student of 2021 Mandarin Language Education Study Program State University of Surabaya there found data with a total number of 18, the examples are such following:

➤ *Data 37*

①成年人不仅关乎身体的成长和②发展。

① *héngnián rén bùjǐn guānhū shēntǐ de chéngzhǎng hé*
② *fāzhǎn*.

① Adulthood is not only about physical growth **and**
② development) (K037/P1/K1/KJG).

The quoted data 37 above is using the cohesive grammatical of conjunction type, marked by the preposition of 和 *hé* (and). On the quotation above, preposition 和 *hé* (and) functioned as the binder of clause ① and clause ②. Because of the existent of cohesive grammatical marker 和 *hé* (and), the relation between clause ① and clause ② is equal, hence, according to the theory of Halliday & Hasan, the cohesive grammatical marker 和 *hé* (and) included in the category of additive conjunction. Therefore, the use of additive conjunction 和 *hé* (and) on the quoted data 37 above indicates a relation of additional explanation, which clause ② gives and additional explanation to clause ①.

➤ Data 38

成年人是一个我们可①以思考，②行动而成熟地③做出决定的过程。

Chéngnián rén shì yīgè wǒmen ①kěyǐ sīkǎo, ②xíngdòng ér chéngshú dì ③zuò chū juédìng de guòchéng.

(Adulthood is a process where we ① could think, ② act, and ③ take decision thoroughly) K028/P1/K1/KJG.

Preposition 而 *ér* (and) on the quoted data 28 above, is a cohesive marker conjunction type with the additive category. Morphologically conjunction type of additive category 而 *ér* (and) is structured as 而且 *érjie* (and), but in its language usage it can be shortened only into the front forming element 而 *ér* (and). In grammatical context as data 28 quoted above, cohesive grammatical marker additive conjunction type serves as a binder of the front statement ① ...可以思考 *kěyǐ sīkǎo* (could think deeply), ② 行动 *xíngdòng* (act) with the following statement ...做出决定 *zuò chū juédìng* (... makes decision). Statement that bound by preposition which categorized as additive conjunction 而 *ér* (and) on the quoted data 28 above owns the equal relations which conveyed the intention of acts that's been doing continuously. This is in accordance with one of the functions of cohesive grammatical marker additive conjunction category 而且 *érjie* (and) or 而 *ér* (and), which to bind two or more of continuous acts.

➤ Data 32

成熟的特点是思想成熟、行为成熟，然后是情感成熟。

chéngshú de tèdiǎn shì sīxiǎng chéngshú, xíngwéi chéngshú, ránhòu shì qínggǎn chéngshú.

(Maturity is characterized by mature thinking, mature behaviour, then mature emotions) K032/P1/K2/KJG.

然后 *ránhòu* (then, afterwards) preposition which used in data 32 quotation above has the function of connecting the clause in front of it with the following clause after it, thus creates an equal relation as presenting information and/or statements in sequence, therefore resulting information and/or plural statement. However, there is no emphasis on one part or contradiction between one piece information and another statement. Each information and/or statement both own the same position or level to mark the existent information and/or a statement more than one. According to the classification and the function of 然后 *ránhòu* (then, afterwards) preposition on the quoted data 32 above, it is valid that this preposition is a cohesive grammatical with the category of additive conjunction type because the existent of this preposition acts as a binder for the elements that form grammatical units so that a coherent and complete text structure can be arrayed.

➤ Data 02

①许多成年人在知道自己不好时会古坏事，给别人天麻烦，② a)当然 b)也会伤害自己。

①Xǔduō chéngnián rén zài zhīdào zìjǐ bù hǎo shí huì gǔ huàishì, gěi biérén tiān máfan, ② a)dāngrán b)yě huì shānghài zìjǐ.

(① Many adults will do bad things even though they know it is not good, causing troubles for others, ② a) certainly b) also harm their own selves) K002/P1/K2/KJG.

The quoted data 02 above owns a preposition with conjunction type, which preposition a) 当然 *dāngrán* (of course/certainly) and preposition b) 也 *yě* (also). The role of b) 也 *yě* (also) preposition shows that it is used to bind two clauses, which are clause ① especially the 给别人天麻烦 *gěi biérén tiān máfan* (causing troubles for others) and clause ②. Preposition 也 *yě* (also) in clause ② is to repeat the object 天麻烦 *tiān máfan* (causing troubles) which consisted in clause ①. The repetitive form is linear, which the object in clause ② is meant to add or aligning the object in clause ①, based on its relation it is valid that preposition 也 *yě* (also) on the text quotation on data 02 above is a cohesive grammatical marker with the category of additive conjunction.

当然 *dāngrán* (of course/certainly) preposition also acts as a conjunction, for it connects clause ① and clause ②. The act of 当然 *dāngrán* (of course/certainly) preposition is to indicate that the following statement 许多成年人在知道自己不好时会古坏事 *Xǔduō chéngnián rén zài zhīdào zìjǐ bù hǎo shí huì gǔ huàishì* (Many adults will do bad things even though they know it is not good) which in the clause ① can generate clause ② or vice versa, clause ② is the result of clause ①. According to the relations that marked with the use of preposition 当然 *dāngrán* (of course/certainly), hence why in correspondence with the concept theory of Halliday & Hasan, the preposition is a marker of grammatical cohesion, a type of conjunction with a clause conjunction category.

B. Causal Conjunction

➤ Data 33

①很多事儿我们自己做了，因为②大多数人都很忙。

①hěnduō shì er wǒmen zìjǐ zuòle, yīnwéi ②dà duōshù rén dōu hěn máng.

(①We do many things ourselves because ②most people are busy) (K033/P1/K3/KJG).

The use of 因为 *yīnwéi* (because) preposition on the quoted data 33 above marks its role as an instrument that connects clause ① and clause ②. The use of the grammatical cohesion marker conjunction indicates the existent of ‘cause’ relations contained in the text quotation. Which in other words, cohesion type of conjunction 因为 *yīnwéi* (because) acts as a marker for clause ② functioning as ‘cause’ while clause ① acts as the effect. There is a dismissal of grammatical cohesion marker conjunction of category ‘cause’ in clause ①, where semantically there should be presented an instrument of conjunction cohesive type with ‘cause’ category before clause ① that is the 所以 *suǒyǐ* (therefore) conjunction. However, according to Mandarin syntax rules, when the clause that acts as ‘cause’ is placed in front, then the instrument of grammatical cohesion conjunction type with clause ‘cause’ category should be removed. And it will be unacceptable the cohesion marker is being presented just as the following sentence (***所以**很多事儿我们自己做了, **因为**②大多数人都很忙). With that being the case, according to Halliday & Hasan’s concept theory, grammatical cohesion that marks the relation of cause and effect as the quoted data 33 above is considered marker of grammatical cohesion, clausal category conjunction type.

➤ Data 51

①因为一个人的成熟度, **如果**②是建立在一个人面对问题的评估之上, **就更合适**。

① *Yīnwéi yīgè rén de chéngshú dù, rúguǒ* ② *shì jiànlì zài yīgè rén miàn duì wèntí de pínggū zhī shàng, jiù gèng héshìle.*

(① Because an individual’s maturity will be more appropriate **if** ② it were based on the individual’s assessment of the problems they face).

The unification of the elements that form the structure of the text unit in data 51 quoted above, one of which is determined by the use of preposition 如果 *rúguǒ* (if). This preposition connects clause ① with clause ② and the presence of preposition 如果 *rúguǒ* (if) results in a prerequisite relation. Which the existence of clause ② is a rule for clause ① to occur, so the existence of clause ② becomes a determining element in being able to generate clause ①. Based on the semantic relation resulting from the use of preposition 如果 *rúguǒ* (if) between the two clauses elements forming grammatical text units 6) above, the classification of this relation is a characteristic of the semantic relation formed by conjunction-type language units. And because the relation between the two clauses is mutual, which that one clause contributes or as a determining rule/condition for the other clause, it can be ascertained that preposition 如果 *rúguǒ* (if) is a marker of grammatical cohesion of the type of clause category conjunction.

➤ Data 51

①他们也意识到生活中有很多东西需要学习, **所以**②最好保持开放的心态。

① *tāmen yě yìshí dào shēnghuó zhōng yǒu hěnduō dōngxī xūyào xuéxí, suǒyǐ* ② *zuì hǎo bǎochí kāifàng de xīntài.*

(① They also realize that there are many things to learn in life, **therefore** ② it’s better to keep an open mind) (K051/P4/K4/KJG).

The use of grammatical cohesion conjunction type’s instrument on the quoted text data 51 above is marked by the existence of preposition 所以 *suǒyǐ* (therefore) that acts as a binder of clause ① and clause ②. According to the relation of both clauses, clause ② holds the role as an ‘effect’ from the clause ①. Occurs a removal of cohesion marker grammatical type with a ‘cause’ category in clause ①, which before the clause ① syntactically it is ideal to present a cohesion instrument conjunction type with the ‘cause’ clausal category namely 因为 *yīnwéi* (because). However, the act of removal in the data 51 quotation above is unacceptable and considered a violation to the rules of Mandarin language syntax. With that being the case, grammatical cohesion marker conjunction type 所以 *suǒyǐ* (therefore) is categorized as clausal conjunction.

C. Adversative Conjunction

➤ Data 31

①成熟**不仅是**身体上的, **而且是**②情感上和社交上的成熟。

① *chéngshú bùjǐn shì shēntǐ shàng de, érqǐě shì* ② *qínggǎn shàng hé shèjiāo shàng de chéngshú.*

(① Maturity is **not only** physical maturity, **but also** ② social and emotional maturity) (K031/P3/K3/KJG).

Preposition 不仅 *bùjǐn* (not only) 而且 *érqǐě* (but also) used in quoted text of data 31 above is classified into grammatical cohesion conjunction type. The grammatical cohesion is marked by the existent words of 而且 *érqǐě* which means (but). The ‘but’ conjunction connects the clause ① “成熟不仅是身体上的” *chéngshú bùjǐn shì shēntǐ shàng de* (maturity is not only physical maturity) with clause ② “是情感上和社交上的成熟” *shì qínggǎn shàng hé shèjiāo shàng de chéngshú* (but also social and emotional maturity). The showing of preposition 不仅 *bùjǐn* (not only) 而且 *érqǐě* (but also) causes the relation of both clauses becomes contradictive. In other words, the case within clause ① is not always identic with clause ②, and vice versa. Therefore, if we associate it with the theory of Halliday & Hasan, speech of data 31 above is included in cohesion grammatical conjunction type with a category of adversative conjunction. Adversative conjunction is a conjunction that binds two clauses or sentences and both sentences or clauses is contradictive or not linear.

➤ Data 06

①成熟是通过我们何思考和处理事物来实现的，而不仅仅因为②年龄。

①chéngshú shì tōngguò wǒmen hé sīkǎo hé chǔlǐ shìwù lái shíxiàn de, ér bùjǐn jǐn yīnwèi ②niánlíng.

(① Maturity pass through us through our way of thinking and processing something, not only because of ② age) (K006/P1/K6/KJG).

Quoted data 06 above uses grammatical cohesion marker conjunction type that marked by the use of preposition 而不仅仅因为 *ér bùjǐn jǐn yīnwèi* (not only because of). Its role as a conjunction can be seen through the preposition function quoted text in data 06 above, in which connects sentence ① with sentence ②. Where grammatically, the sentence structure of ② in a complete form would be 成熟是而不仅仅因为年龄 *chéngshú shì ér bùjǐn jǐn yīnwèi niánlíng* (Maturity is not only because of age). In that case, the use of preposition 而不仅仅因为 *ér bùjǐn jǐn yīnwèi* (not only because of) on the data 06 quotation above can be confirmed as a grammatical cohesion conjunction type. With the use of that conjunction, it results a contradictive or not linear relation between the two sentences. It is proven that the statement in sentence ① is not similar and/or will not necessarily form the sentence ②, and vice versa. Thereof, the grammatical cohesion conjunction type in the quoted text of data 06 above is conforming to the theory concept of Halliday & Hasan including the conjunction type with adversative category.

➤ Data 01

①一般来说，成年人这个词的含义总是指一个人的年龄。但是，②我认为成年是一种成熟的心态

①Yībān lái shuō, chéngnián rén zhège cí de hányì zǒng shì zhī yīgè rén de niánlíng. Dànshì, ②wǒ rènwéi chéngnián shì yī zhǒng chéngshú de xīntài. (① Generally, the word mature always refers to an individual's age. But, ② for me maturity is a circumstance where maturity is a mature mind) (K039/P1/K2/KJG).

The quoted data 01 above is an example of the use of cohesion marker conjunction type in a discourse text which marked by the word 但是 *dànshì* (but). Based on its function in data 01 above, the preposition connects clause ① and clause ②, where clause ① acts as refuted or disproved statement, meanwhile clause ② as a reasoning of conveying rejection. Observing the relation caused by preposition 但是 *dànshì* (but), therefore it is approved as grammatical cohesion marker corelation conjunction type. And observing the existent relation between the two clauses as an outcome from the use of grammatical cohesion marker 但是 *dànshì* (but), hence the grammatical cohesion is categorized an adversative conjunction type. This fact is in accordance with the concept theory of Halliday & Hasan, viz adversative is a conjunction marker that binds opposition or contradiction

relations. Although the developed relations by the use of preposition 但是 *dànshì* (but) is naturally contradictory, but from the aspect of structure and meaning the text itself is both cohesive and coherent, thus the grammatical cohesion with adversative conjunction type acts as a binding element of the text's coherence structural.

➤ Data 17

尽管①成年人已年满 17 岁，但是②客际上有年轻人和成年人。

Jǐnguǎn ①chéngnián rén yǐ nián mǎn 17 suì, dànshì ②kè jì shàng yǒu niánqīng rén hé chéngnián rén.

(Although ① grown-ups are aged above 17 years old, but ② truth be told there are youngsters and adults) K017/P1/K1/RPT.

Preposition 尽管 ... 但是 *jǐnguǎn... dànshì* (although...but) in quoted data 17 above is an example of the grammatical cohesion marker conjunction type, with a reason that the preposition owns the role to bind two clauses, viz clause ① with clause ②. Based on the relations within two clauses developed by the conjunction 尽管...但是 *jǐnguǎn... dànshì* (although...but), viz clause ① is a refuted or denied statement, meanwhile clause ② acts as a denier argument or statement. In that case, grammatical cohesion marker 尽管...但是 *jǐnguǎn... dànshì* (although...but) can be confirmed as a grammatical cohesion marker correlation conjunction type. Which marked correlation or the relation of clause ① with clause ② itself. Since the conjunction 尽管...但是 *jǐnguǎn... dànshì* (although...but) on the data 17 quotation above resulting the contradiction relation, then according to Halliday & Hasan's concept theory, viz the grammatical cohesion marker is considered an adversative categorized conjunction.

VI. SUMMARY

According to the results of analysed data presented above, it can be concluded that grammatical cohesion marker conjunction type that is used by the student of 2021 Mandarin Language Education Program Study of State University of Surabaya involves categories of additive, clausal, and adversative conjunction. Additive conjunction functions as a marker of equal relations, applied through the use of conjunction 和 *hé* (and) to mark the type of relation that equal without emphasizing on one object or statement. Then a category of additive conjunction 而 *ér* (and) is used to deliver an equal meaning relation of an activity which done continuously without emphasizing on either meaning. The use of other grammatical cohesion additive conjunction category is also marked by the use of preposition 也 *yě* (also) which functions to deliver an equal relation and emphasize the front unit or an existent similarity with the

unit previously mentioned. The use of grammatical cohesion marker with additive conjunction category is also marked by the use of preposition 然后 *ránhòu* (then, afterwards) that is used to convey a meaning of equal relations which done or stated consecutively and continuously.

Grammatical cohesion marker conjunction type with clausal category is also found in the student of 2021 Mandarin Language Education Study Program of State University of Surabaya. One of which is the use of preposition 因为 *yīnwéi* (because) as a conjunction that marked an occurrence or the ‘cause’ and occurs a removal on a result or the ‘effect’ marker, preposition 所以 *suǒyǐ* (therefore) as a conjunction that marked results or the effect and occurs a removal on the ‘cause’ marker, 当然 *dāngrán* (absolutely, certainly) as a conjunction that indicates or marked a result that does not need a ‘cause’ marker preposition or a determining and conclusion marker, also the use of preposition 因为 *yīnwéi* (because)... 所以 *suǒyǐ* (therefore), viz a form of conjunction that indicates a formal relations of cause-and-effect. And then, the use of conjunction categorized as adversative which indicated by the existent 不仅 *bùjǐn* (not only) 而且 *érqiě* (but also) preposition, the use of preposition 而不仅仅因为 *ér bùjǐn jǐn yīnwéi* (not only because), preposition 但是 *dànshì* (but), and the use of preposition 尽管...但是 *jǐnguǎn... dànshì* (although ... but) that indicates a contradictory relation on one preposition to another.

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